

Deep Learning Tool for Nuclear Forensics and Uncertainty Quantification

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ABSTRACT

The objective of this research is to produce a computational nuclear forensics tool with deep learning to compare computer model generated data and experimental data, and fine tune input parameters to recreate the initial conditions of the nuclear forensics' problems. Nuclear forensics problems explore a range of solutions which are influenced by uncertainty quantification, noisy data sets, and time. There is a need to screen large parametric domains associated with potential interconnections within nuclear forensic scenarios that may facilitate solutions. This will result in a reduction in computational cost because it will allow for a range of potential solutions from simulations to be analyzed. Which also requires many simulations to be run and postprocessed/analyzed. This will allow for many simulations to be run in advance which can be used as training data and the complex relationships can be evaluated using a neural network. The tool would explore recreating initial conditions from reaction rates of irradiated samples. Additionally, the ability to see how different nuclear data inputs affect the solution ranges will allow for the quantification of nuclear data uncertainties in nuclear forensics problems and reactor physics. This will be of great benefit for the nuclear forensics field, contemporary and advanced reactors, nuclear security, safeguards, and nonproliferation.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Nuclear Forensics, Nuclear Security

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence and deep learning are powerful tools that can be used to predict behaviors in a variety of different settings. [1] Artificial intelligence is the broader term referring to deep learning and other techniques which can be used to create a system which has learning capabilities. Deep learning is a subset of artificial intelligence with the distinction of focusing primarily on developing neural networks with multiple layers which can be trained to make predictions. Deep learning algorithms have been used in a variety of nuclear forensics applications, such as fission track analysis, advancing nuclear data, and analysis using machine learning enabled laser induced breakdown spectroscopy. [2][3][4] The advantages of these tools are that they can handle large amounts of data, automate processes, and find new correlations in data which were not initially noticeable. In this case, it would be used to predict the initial conditions of nuclear reactions based on final conditions or the produced nuclides.

Nuclear Forensics problems require time sensitive solutions utilizing deep learning techniques could assist in reducing the time or computational cost. Typically, in a nuclear forensics problem, products of an irradiation are analyzed to determine the initial materials irradiated. This is a nonlinear problem, where the output is not linearly proportional to the input. Many simulations of probable solutions have to be run to determine the solution to a nuclear forensics problem. The time it takes to analyze the solutions can be reduced by implementing a neural network. The input parameters would be initial conditions for the reactions that produce the products being analyzed. The nuclear forensics tool could also analyze cases where multiple solutions could be postulated. However, this may require a classification component to the algorithm.

Nuclear data is the basis of all nuclear engineering and cross sections are necessary to perform most nuclear evaluations. A nuclear cross section can be interpreted as both a probability that a reaction will occur and a unit of area which quantifies the likelihood of the interaction occurring between the incident particle and the nucleus. The neutron microscopic cross section is a function of energy and can be divided into four regions when plotted against energy. The thermal energy region follows a $1/v$ or

1/SQRT(E) behavior. The next region is the resolved resonance region followed by the unresolved resonance region and finally the fast or high energy region. Cross sections are measured using differential measurements which directly evaluate cross sections through experiments. The cross section is the driving factor in reaction rates, for instance equation 1. [5]

$$RR=N\sigma\phi \quad (1)$$

Where,

RR is the reaction rate,

N is the atom density,

σ is the cross section, and

Φ is the flux.

The reaction rate will be used in evaluating the atom density produced and used to inversely determine the initial atom densities of the irradiated samples.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Overview of Deep Learning Model

For the final product of the deep learning model, data will be collected from a benchmark of critical assembly experiments. Test cases will be produced using MCNP based on the benchmarks to test the deep learning model. MCNP is a particle transport code used to produce simulations of critical assemblies in this case. [6] Data from the MCNP output files will be post processed to be multiplied by the atom density and to be decay corrected. The activation products will be the input parameters. Then, the relationships within the data will be evaluated by a neural network and the neural network architecture will be developed. The general structure of the model will follow Figure 1. The approach as displayed in Figure 1 is as follows: Run simulations producing calculations of the reaction rates by changing the initial conditions prior to the irradiation. Then post process the output of the simulation to get activated products. Once the data is collected the activation products can be input into a neural network to perform a regression to find the initial materials prior to irradiation. The learned gradient can be used to provide a prediction of the initial materials from the activation products of an experiment. Based on the prediction the simulation parameters can be adjusted to fit the experiment. For example, the cross sections could be changed from one library to another.

Figure 1. An outline of the overall structure.

2.1.1. Dual Head Structure: Regression and Classification Components

The Nuclear forensics tool will consist of a dual head neural network. There will be a head for regression and a head for classification. Classification Models use an algorithm within a neural network to sort

data into categories/classes. Regression Models are like the classification model except it uses neural networks to solve regression problems. Which are tasks where the goal is to predict continuous values, not categories. The regression head will determine initial quantities of the materials, so it will output the initial atom densities. The classification head will match products with initial materials, so it will output the isotopes of interest. The utilization of a regression model is helpful because the problem is nonlinear. The training phase of the dual head neural network would be to teach the neural network and sharpen the algorithm regarding the classification of various items and the prediction of initial material atom densities from the product atom densities. The first couple of layers of the neural network can be shared, and the loss functions would be combined in a total loss function. For uncertainty quantification Monte Carlo Drop out method can be applied to the architecture to quantify epistemic uncertainty for the model. Epistemic uncertainty being the uncertainty that arises from the lack of knowledge or information about a model and aleatoric uncertainty being from the inherent variability in a model that can't be reduced by gathering more data.

2.1.2. Data Collection and Proof of Concept

A simulation of a flattop Plutonium core critical assembly was executed in MCNP to determine the activation product quantities of a stainless-steel foil located at the center of the critical assembly. The activation products of interest were ^{58}Co , ^{57}Co , ^{51}Cr , ^{54}Mn , ^{59}Fe , and ^{60}Co . The equation used to determine the activation product number of nuclei (N_p) at the end of the irradiation was as follows in equation 2. [7]

$$N_p = \frac{N_T \phi \sigma (1 - e^{-\lambda_p t})}{\lambda_p} \quad (2)$$

Where,

N_T is the number of target nuclei,

N_p is the number of product nuclei,

λ_p is the decay constant,

t is the time,

Φ is the flux, and

σ is the microscopic cross section.

The flux (Φ) was acquired using the F4 tally. The microscopic cross sections (σ) were accounted for using the FM4 multiplier and appropriate reaction. The atoms for each activation product were normalized to the mass of stainless steel and then divided by ^{54}Mn atom density. The atom density of ^{54}Mn was used as a monitor isotope for power normalization. For the experimental data, the sample was irradiated at the National Criticality Experiments Research Center through the NA-22 Nuclear Forensics Venture.[8] The stainless-steel sample was evaluated using a High Purity Germanium (HPGe) detector. The atom densities of the isotopes of interest were calculated using the activity from the HPGe which was decay corrected. The gamma spectrum that was acquired from the HPGe detector for the stainless steel sample can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Gamma Spectra of the stainless-steel sample.

A regression model was initially developed for this data generated with the intention of being a proof of concept. So, the training data was the normalized product atom densities and the initial material atom densities which were collected from MCNP and post processed. The testing data was the normalized product atom densities from the HPGe/experimental derived. The results of the regression neural network model can be seen in the preliminary results section. At the time of writing this paper more data is being generated, and other components of the deep learning forensics tool are being developed.

3. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

The regression model has 5 linear layers and 4 activation functions which were the rectified linear unit (ReLU). The preliminary results for the training and testing of regression neural network are displayed in Figures 3 and 4. Figure 3 is the comparison of predictions by the neural network to the true value of initial material atom densities for the computational data or MCNP generated data. Figure 4 is the comparison of predictions by the neural network to the true value of initial material atom densities for the experimental data or HPGe generated data. As is displayed in Figures 3 and 4, the initial regression model displays that the learned parameters from the training data can be applied to the testing data to make close estimates for the experimental data. For ^{51}Cr there is a slight difference when the network is applied to the experimental data and that is because of the discrepancies between the simulation and the experimentally derive results. Also, ^{51}Cr has three reaction pathways that produce it. The loss curve for the regression model is provided in Figure 5. The loss curve displays the loss versus the number of epochs that the model was trained for. The learning rate was set to 0.0001 which provided an acceptable loss convergence. There was no need for a classification model with this data because only one sample was analyzed, this will change as more simulations are run and post processed for a database.

Figure 3. Comparison of predictions to the true values for the computational data.

Figure 4. Comparison of predictions to the true values for the experimental data.

Figure 5. Loss curve which displays the loss versus the number of epochs.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the initial regression model developed the structure of the regression neural network can be used as a starting point for the development of a dual head neural network to achieve the goal of the development of a nuclear forensics tool. The goal being to recreate initial conditions from reaction rates of irradiated samples and to reduce computational time. Additionally, as more data is generated the regression architecture would naturally have to be adjusted by adding more layers or reducing the number of layers to suit the complexity of the data. Also, to investigate the nuclear data effects on the simulations different cross section libraries could be used to execute the simulations and generate data. Then deviations could be quantified between testing and training data and uncertainty in the neural network could be quantified using the Monte Carlo drop out method. There have been studies that have found that switching the cross-section library can result in an eigenvalue difference of up to 450 pcm.[9] The initial parameters of simulations can be fine tuned to provide activation products closer to the true results.

NOMENCLATURE

HPGE detector is a High Purity Germanium detector, and
MCNP is Monte Carlo n-particle transport code.

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